

UV-Spectra of Some Monofluophosphates

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Monofluophosphates of sodium, potassium, ammonium, cadmium, nickel, manganese, iron (iii) and chromium (iii) were prepared¹ and their absorption spectra were measured from 185 to 300 $m\mu$ with non recording type Hilger Uvispek photoelectric spectrophotometer using one cm. quartz cells which had been matched against each other. The light source used was hydrogen discharge lamp. The solution of the soluble salts were made of known

strength, but the solution of sparingly soluble salts could not be prepared of exact strength. The extinction or absorbance is plotted against wave length in millimicrons. The values of extinction and extinction coefficient were calculated by the formula of Bunsen and Roscoe² based on the Beer's and Lambert's law.

DISCUSSION

From the observation of the spectrophotometric data and the plot of absorbance against wave length it is found that the sodium, potassium, and ammonium monofluophosphates have got sharp peak (maximum absorption) at 189 $m\mu$. In case of nickel monofluophosphates it shifts to slightly higher wave length and the absorption maximum in this case is at 191 $m\mu$. The absorption of monofluophosphates of cadmium, manganese, iron and chromium are not so simple. More than one peak has been obtained in these cases but each of them has got a distinctive peak at 191-192 $m\mu$. The broad absorption band in the above

1. E. B. Singh and P. C. Sinha, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **41**, 407,
2. W. R. Brode, "Chemical Spectroscopy", second edn., page 109, John Wiley and Sons.

cases may be due to different possible energy differences on account of the vibrational and rotational motions accompanying the electronic excitation. The shift in the position of the absorption maximum and the number of peaks may also be due to the nature and weight of the cation attached to the ligand. However the peak at 189-192 $m\mu$ is characteristic

for PO_3F ion as seen in all these cases. Phosphates ion in aq. soln. has also got absorption maxima near about 194-196 $m\mu$ ³ and we may correlate the maxima to the $P = O$ bond in PO_3F which may be taken as chromophoric group having selective absorption at about 189-192 $m\mu$.

It has been noticed that the absorption spectra of the monofluophosphates in aq. soln. vary slightly with concentration and age of the solution. This may be due to the slow hydrolysis that goes on in the dilute solution producing orthophosphoric acid and hydrogen fluoride.

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3. Buck, Singhadeja and Rogers, *Anal. Chem.*, 1954, 26, 1240.